

Objections to a Reply of Oberlack et al.

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Abstract

The published Reply [Phys. Rev. E **92**, 067002 \(2015\)](#) of Oberlack et al. to our Comment [Phys. Rev. E **92**, 067001 \(2015\)](#) contains a new but central reasoning error which unfortunately passed the peer-review process, a mistake which when corrected would lead to an overall opposite conclusion. This notification serves to correct the mistake and will give its correct conclusion instead. Next to this issue, which is discussed in the first two sections, we also list four other, independent objections.

Objection No. 1:

In the Reply of Waclawczyk & Oberlack (2015) it is claimed that Eq. (13) results from Eq. (12) when considering the streamwise variation $\partial/\partial x$ of it. Although Eq. (12)[†] represents an integral equation for the pressure field $P(\mathbf{x})$, its reduction to Eq. (13) under the given assumptions, however, only leads to a trivial identity relation from which no conclusions can be drawn; and *not* to an equation which can be explicitly solved for the pressure gradient as it is misleadingly claimed in the Reply. The problem is that Eq. (13) is presented in a form which does not immediately reveal itself as an identity, simply because the assumptions which were made on the unknown pressure field $P(\mathbf{x})$ (for a laminar plane channel flow) were only made on the right-hand side of Eq. (12). But, in order to yield a consistent equation, these assumptions must also be made on its left-hand side. Hence, the correct formulation of Eq. (13) reads

$$\frac{\Delta P}{2L_x} = -\frac{1}{8L_z H} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_{-H}^H \int_{-L_z}^{L_z} \left[\left(-\frac{\Delta P}{2L_x} |x - x'| \right) \Big|_{x'=-L_x} + \left(\frac{\Delta P}{2L_x} |x - x'| \right) \Big|_{x'=L_x} \right] dz' dy'. \quad (1.1)$$

Now, since the quantity $\Delta P/(2L_x)$ is treated as a constant, it can be taken in front of the integral operations; similar with the evaluations of $|x - x'|$, since the integrations are not performed in

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[†]Note that Eq. (12) is Green's Theorem (see e.g. Jackson (1998))

$$\int_V (\phi \nabla^2 \psi - \psi \nabla^2 \phi) d^3x = \int_S \mathbf{n} \cdot (\phi \nabla \psi - \psi \nabla \phi) d^2x,$$

for $\phi = P$ and $\psi = G$, if the Green function G is normalized to $\nabla^2 G = \delta^3(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}')$. Further note that although Green's Theorem is a valid integral relation, it's not a constructive relation to solve for P in terms of boundary data if both the boundary values of P and $\partial P/\partial \mathbf{n}$ have to be specified simultaneously (Jackson, 1998). Only when choosing the appropriate Green function, this integral relation can be identified as a true integral equation for the unknown pressure field P . Hence, since for P (in the incompressible case) only Neumann boundary conditions can be placed, a consistent integral equation is only obtained if the Green function is chosen such that it satisfies the homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions $\partial G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')/\partial \mathbf{n}' = 0$.

the streamwise direction x . The above equation thus turns into the identity relation

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Delta P}{2L_x} &= -\frac{1}{8L_z H} \frac{\Delta P}{2L_x} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(-|x-x'| \Big|_{x'=-L_x} + |x-x'| \Big|_{x'=L_x} \right) \int_{-H}^H \int_{-L_z}^{L_z} dz' dy' \\ &\stackrel{=}{=} -\frac{1}{8L_z H} \frac{\Delta P}{2L_x} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (-2x) \int_{-H}^H \int_{-L_z}^{L_z} dz' dy' \\ &= \frac{\Delta P}{2L_x}, \end{aligned} \quad (1.2)$$

from which no further conclusions can be drawn; this result doesn't say anything on whether the streamwise pressure gradient $\Delta P/2L_x$ is zero or not. In particular, we do not obtain any explicit non-zero value, e.g. $-2\rho\nu U_0/H^2$ as it's misleadingly argued by Oberlack et al; for that we need additional information from outside.

Objection No. 2:

In going from Eq. (12) to Eq. (13), Oberlack et al. used the Green function for a rectangular duct flow taken from Newman (1992), which again has been taken from Breit (1991). Let us see what happens if we re-evaluate Eq. (12) for the Green function of a pure plane channel exactly as it is also derived and used in these two studies, and *not* for the duct flow as particularly performed by Oberlack et al. According to Breit (1991) the asymptotic scaling of the Green function for a rectangular duct is different to that of a plane channel. In the streamwise direction the former asymptotically scales as[†]

$$G \sim |x|, \quad \text{for } |x| \rightarrow \infty, \quad (2.1)$$

while the latter (for a finite spanwise value z) only scales as[‡]

$$G \sim \log |x|, \quad \text{for } |x| \rightarrow \infty. \quad (2.2)$$

Under the same assumptions again as given in the Reply on the unknown pressure field $P(\mathbf{x})$ for a laminar plane channel flow, but now for the correct Green function (A.7), the general relation in Eq. (12), when considering its streamwise variation

$$\frac{\partial P(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_{\Omega} G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') \nabla'^2 P(\mathbf{x}') dV' + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_{\Gamma} P(\mathbf{x}') \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')}{\partial \mathbf{n}'} dS' - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_{\Gamma} G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') \frac{\partial P(\mathbf{x}')}{\partial \mathbf{n}'} dS', \quad (2.3)$$

then reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta x} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_{\Gamma} P(\mathbf{x}') \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')}{\partial \mathbf{n}'} dS' - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_{\Gamma} G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') \frac{\partial P(\mathbf{x}')}{\partial \mathbf{n}'} dS' \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^6 \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int P(\mathbf{x}') \mathbf{n}'_{(i)} \cdot \nabla' G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') dS'_{(i)} - \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta x} \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') n'_{x,(i)} dS'_{(i)}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

[†]For more details, see also the Appendix where we summarized the results of Breit (1991).

[‡]Note that a Green function is unique up to a linear function in the coordinates, when considering only the single condition $\nabla^2 G = \delta^3(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}')$. However, in order to operate with a *universal* Green function of a Neumann problem, e.g. which can be applied in Eq.(12) as well as later also in Eq. (14), the only option to ensure full consistency is to require homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions for the Green function on *all* surfaces of the integration domain. Then the Green function is unique only up to an additive constant. Hence, since the Green function with the linear scaling (2.1) doesn't meet this universal condition, it therefore only applies to Eq. (12) for the pressure, and *not* to Eq. (14) for the PDF field; a universal Green function for a duct, however, can be found e.g. in Polyanin (2002), which instead of $|x|$ then asymptotically scales as $e^{-|x|}$.

where the six surfaces $S'_{(i)}$ of the boundary $\Gamma = \partial\Omega$ of the unbounded plane channel domain

$$\Omega = \lim_{L_x, L_z \rightarrow \infty} (-L_x, L_x) \times [-H, H] \times (-L_z, L_z), \quad (2.5)$$

are ordered as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} S'_{(1)}: & \quad x' = L_x, \quad -H \leq y' \leq H, \quad -L_z \leq z' \leq L_z; \quad \mathbf{n}'_{(1)} = (1, 0, 0), \\ S'_{(2)}: & \quad x' = -L_x, \quad -H \leq y' \leq H, \quad -L_z \leq z' \leq L_z; \quad \mathbf{n}'_{(2)} = (-1, 0, 0), \\ S'_{(3)}: & \quad -L_x \leq x' \leq L_x, \quad y' = H, \quad -L_z \leq z' \leq L_z; \quad \mathbf{n}'_{(3)} = (0, 1, 0), \\ S'_{(4)}: & \quad -L_x \leq x' \leq L_x, \quad y' = -H, \quad -L_z \leq z' \leq L_z; \quad \mathbf{n}'_{(4)} = (0, -1, 0), \\ S'_{(5)}: & \quad -L_x \leq x' \leq L_x, \quad -H \leq y' \leq H, \quad z' = L_z; \quad \mathbf{n}'_{(5)} = (0, 0, 1), \\ S'_{(6)}: & \quad -L_x \leq x' \leq L_x, \quad -H \leq y' \leq H, \quad z' = -L_z; \quad \mathbf{n}'_{(6)} = (0, 0, -1). \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2.6)$$

Now, before we insert the Green function (A.7) for the plane channel into equation (2.4), we first have to fix the correct normalization constant such that it is consistent with Eq. (12). Since the Green function in Eq. (12) is normalized to

$$\nabla^2 G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = \delta^3(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'), \quad (2.7)$$

while (A.7) is normalized to

$$\nabla^2 G^{\text{Breit}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = -4\pi\delta^3(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'), \quad (2.8)$$

we have to re-scale the normalization constant accordingly. Hence, the correctly normalized Green function for plane channel to be inserted into (2.4) is thus given as

$$G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = G_0(x - x', z - z'; y - y') + G_0(x - x', z - z'; y + y' + 2H), \quad (2.9)$$

where

$$G_0(x, z; y) = \frac{1}{8\pi H} \left(\gamma + \ln \frac{\sqrt{x^2 + z^2}}{8H} \right) - \frac{1}{4\pi H} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} K_0(\pi n \sqrt{x^2 + z^2}/2H) \cos(\pi n y/2H). \quad (2.10)$$

Since this Green function (2.9) by construction satisfies the homogeneous Neumann boundary condition on *all* six surfaces (2.6) of the integration domain (2.5)

$$\mathbf{n}'_{(i)} \cdot \nabla' G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') \Big|_{\mathbf{x}' \in S'_{(i)}} = 0, \quad \forall i, \quad L_x, L_z \rightarrow \infty, \quad (2.11)$$

and therefore representing a *universal* Green function of the underlying Neumann problem matching the conditions to be later also used in Eq. (14) of the Reply, equation (2.4) further reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta x} &= -\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta x} \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') n'_{x,(i)} dS'_{(i)} \\ &= -\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta x} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_{-H}^H \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \lim_{L_x \rightarrow \infty} \left(G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') \Big|_{x'=L_x} - G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') \Big|_{x'=-L_x} \right) dz' dy' \\ &= -\frac{1}{4\pi H} \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta x} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \int_{-H}^H \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \lim_{L_x \rightarrow \infty} \left(\ln \frac{\sqrt{(x - L_x)^2 + (z - z')^2}}{\sqrt{(x + L_x)^2 + (z - z')^2}} \right) dz' dy' \\ &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

Hence, for plane laminar channel flow the pressure field in Eq. (12) evaluates to zero, independent of whether we take the streamwise variation of Eq. (12) or not, since we haven't had to make use of the partial derivative $\partial/\partial x$ to obtain result (2.12), that means, result (2.12) can also be equivalently formulated as

$$P(\mathbf{x}) = -\frac{1}{4\pi H} \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta x} \int_{-H}^H \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \lim_{L_x \rightarrow \infty} \left(\ln \frac{\sqrt{(x-L_x)^2 + (z-z')^2}}{\sqrt{(x+L_x)^2 + (z-z')^2}} \right) dz' dy' = 0. \quad (2.13)$$

Important to note here is that when performing the above evaluation, the order of the mathematical operations is essential, i.e. the streamwise limit does not commute with the spanwise integral operation. That equation (2.12) is evaluated correctly, can also be seen when applying Green's Theorem

$$\int_V (\phi \nabla^2 \psi - \psi \nabla^2 \phi) d^3x = \int_S \mathbf{n} \cdot (\phi \nabla \psi - \psi \nabla \phi) d^2x, \quad (2.14)$$

directly for the pressure-gradient field $\partial P/\partial x$, i.e. instead of choosing $\phi = P$ we now take $\phi = \partial P/\partial x$. For the domain $V = \Omega$ (2.5) and for $\psi = G$, where the Green function G is again normalized to $\nabla^2 G = \delta^3(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}')$, the relation (2.14) will read

$$\frac{\partial P(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x} = \int_{\Omega} G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') \nabla'^2 \frac{\partial P(\mathbf{x}')}{\partial x'} + \int_{\Gamma} \frac{\partial P(\mathbf{x}')}{\partial x'} \frac{\partial G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')}{\partial \mathbf{n}'} dS' - \int_{\Gamma} G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{n}'} \frac{\partial P(\mathbf{x}')}{\partial x'} dS'. \quad (2.15)$$

With the assumptions for a laminar plane channel flow as given in the Reply, and by taking the correct Green function (2.9)-(2.10), the right-side of (2.15) will naturally evaluate to zero. The first and third integral are zero due to the assumption that a constant streamwise pressure gradient $\partial P(\mathbf{x}')/\partial x' = \Delta P/\Delta x$ is applied, and the second integral is zero due to the fact that the correct Green function G (2.9)-(2.10) satisfies homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions (2.11) on *all* surfaces of the integration domain Ω (2.5) — a condition which is necessary later when considering Eq. (14). Hence, the result (2.13) is naturally confirmed.

Conclusion: Opposite to the conclusion given in the Reply, the integral relation Eq. (12) either leads to the indifferent and thus inconclusive result $\Delta P/\Delta x = \Delta P/\Delta x$ when considering a Green function of a duct in showing compatibility only to the conditions of Eq. (13), or it invariably leads to the result $P = 0$ when considering a Green function of a plane channel being compatible to the conditions of Eq. (13) and Eq. (14).[†] At first sight the latter result seems to be a contradiction, because how can it be that the pressure gradient is non-zero while the pressure field itself is zero? By a simple re-interpretation of the problem, however, this contradiction can be easily resolved. Because as the problem shows, the (external) pressure gradient cannot be consistently incorporated into the geometric (internal) Green functions in a universal way. Hence, the method of Green functions thus shows that in order to have a well-posed and meaningful mathematical formulation, the external pressure gradient either has to be explicitly added to the pressure field itself, as e.g. done in McComb (1990), or it has to be added as a source term to the underlying dynamical equations; but not as a supporting element in the Green functions, obviously because the external pressure gradient is not an internal property

[†]In this regard it is worthwhile to note that although the geometry of the plane (two-sided open) channel can be viewed as a (infinite) limiting case of the duct (one-sided open channel), this is *not* the case for the corresponding Green functions, being reflected in two completely different asymptotic scaling behaviors (2.1) and (2.2). The reason is that the Green function for the duct is double-periodic while for the plane channel only single-periodic in the wall-normal directions, which is a counter-intuitive result stemming from the image-construction principle of these functions (see e.g. Jackson (1998)). In other words, the asymptotic result for a plane channel (2.2) can *not* be obtained from the full Green function of the duct in the limit of $L_z \rightarrow \infty$; for more details, see the Appendix. This is what Newman (1992) also calls to be a result of complementary domains, i.e. the Green function for a wide duct acts in a complementary domain to that of a plane channel.

of the flow itself. Such an approach would only destroy the universality of the Green function in that it would not be applicable anymore to *all* possible flow configurations within a fixed prescribed geometry. In how this formal method of Green functions is applied correctly for a pressure driven channel flow in the case of adding an explicit source term to the transport equations, we refer to our latest version of Frewer *et al.* (2014). Therein we also clearly show that the so-called "shape-symmetry" proposed by Oberlack *et al.* induces contradictions in the equations for the moments, independent of whether spatial boundaries are considered or not. Hence, this "shape-symmetry" is thus not only physically but also mathematically inconsistent.

Objection No. 3:

Considering the previous result and conclusion that the external pressure gradient in channel flow cannot be *universally* incorporated into the Green function but that it instead has to be placed e.g. as a source term in the underlying dynamical equations, leaves the first impression that in the derived LMN hierarchy, as presented by Eq. (14) in the Reply, this fact has been taken into account too. Because, next to the Green function an additional pressure gradient term, namely the second term on the right-hand side of Eq. (14), has been added to the LMN hierarchy. But, adding only this term is not sufficient. The reason for it lies in the asymptotic structure of any *universal* Green function of a Neumann problem, because e.g. for plane channel flow (2.9)-(2.10) this function G , which satisfies the given condition $\partial G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')/\partial \mathbf{n}' = 0$ (2.11) for Eq. (14), is structured such that any of its variations gives no contributions on the streamwise and spanwise surfaces (2.6) in the limit $(L_x, L_z) \rightarrow \infty$, that means, due to

$$\nabla_{(j)} G(\mathbf{x}_{(j)}, \mathbf{x}_{(n+1)}) \Big|_{\mathbf{x}_{(n+1)} \in S_{(n+1)}^{(k)}} = 0, \quad \text{for } k = 1, 2 \text{ (streamwise surfaces), } L_x \rightarrow \infty \\ \text{and } k = 5, 6 \text{ (spanwise surfaces), } L_z \rightarrow \infty, \quad (3.1)$$

we experience the following reduction of this additional, second term[†]

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{j=1}^n \nabla_{\mathbf{v}_{(j)}} \cdot \left\{ \int_{\Gamma} \left(\nabla_{(j)} G(\mathbf{x}_{(j)}, \mathbf{x}_{(n+1)}) \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. \cdot \int \left\langle \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P(\mathbf{x}_{(n+1)})}{\partial \mathbf{n}_{(n+1)}} \Big|_{\mathbf{v}_{(1)} = \mathbf{U}_{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{(n+1)} = \mathbf{U}_{(n+1)}} \right\rangle f_{n+1} d\mathbf{v}_{(n+1)} \right) dS_{(n+1)} \right\} \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^n \nabla_{\mathbf{v}_{(j)}} \cdot \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_{(n+1)} dz_{(n+1)} \left(\nabla_{(j)} G(\mathbf{x}_{(j)}, \mathbf{x}_{(n+1)}) \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. \cdot \int \left\langle \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P(\mathbf{x}_{(n+1)})}{\partial y_{(n+1)}} \Big|_{\mathbf{v}_{(1)} = \mathbf{U}_{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{(n+1)} = \mathbf{U}_{(n+1)}} \right\rangle f_{n+1} d\mathbf{v}_{(n+1)} \right) \Big|_{y_{(n+1)}=H} \right\} \\ & \quad - \sum_{j=1}^n \nabla_{\mathbf{v}_{(j)}} \cdot \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_{(n+1)} dz_{(n+1)} \left(\nabla_{(j)} G(\mathbf{x}_{(j)}, \mathbf{x}_{(n+1)}) \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. \cdot \int \left\langle \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P(\mathbf{x}_{(n+1)})}{\partial y_{(n+1)}} \Big|_{\mathbf{v}_{(1)} = \mathbf{U}_{(1)}, \dots, \mathbf{v}_{(n+1)} = \mathbf{U}_{(n+1)}} \right\rangle f_{n+1} d\mathbf{v}_{(n+1)} \right) \Big|_{y_{(n+1)}=-H} \right\}, \quad (3.2) \end{aligned}$$

[†]Of course, by relaxing the condition $G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')/\partial \mathbf{n}' = 0$, e.g. to allow for Green functions which asymptotically scale as $|x|$ in the streamwise direction, we will evidently obtain a mean pressure gradient in Eq. (14), but then at the price of having to impose *unnatural* restrictions on the PDF field f_{n+1} (e.g. to ensure a general convergence in the unbounded volume integral), which may even put the well-posedness of the whole problem to question. For a *universal* Green function, however, strictly satisfying $G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')/\partial \mathbf{n}' = 0$ on *all* boundaries of the integration domain, the problem is well-posed as no such restrictions do exist.

which obviously does not include any contributions from a mean streamwise pressure-gradient term of the form $\langle \partial P / \partial x \rangle$. Hence, the LMN hierarchy for a plane channel flow as presented by Eq. (14) does not contain a mean pressure gradient to drive the flow as misleadingly claimed in the Reply.

Objection No. 4:

Knowing that Eq. (14) is incomplete, in that it cannot account for a mean pressure gradient in the PDF transport equations when applying the correct Green function, the aim is now to add the correct missing terms to Eq. (14). Following e.g. the derivation of Lundgren (1967) and adjusting it to the present case of a bounded channel flow driven by a constant streamwise pressure gradient, the right-hand side of Eq. (14) has to be extended or supplemented by the terms

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \nabla_{(i)} P_0 \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{v}_{(i)}} f_n, \quad (4.1)$$

where $\nabla_{(i)} P_0 = (K, 0, 0), \forall i$, is the constant streamwise pressure gradient denoted by the single number $K \neq 0$ to drive the flow. This change in the PDF equations now has a considerable effect on the "shape-symmetry" given by Eq. (8) in the Reply. Because, if Oberlack et al. claims that Eq. (14) stays invariant under Eq. (8), as they do on p. 4 after Eq. (19), then the additional pressure terms (4.1) are just symmetry-breaking, simply because when they are transformed they give non-vanishing contributions due to the operator $\nabla_{\mathbf{v}_{(i)}}$ which cannot be cancelled by the other terms in Eq. (14), since, according to Oberlack et al., their equation (14) as a whole strictly stays invariant — in particular, since the symmetry breaking contributions from (4.1) are dependent on K , while Eq. (14) is independent of K (due to the result of Objection No. 3) and thus unable to induce possible counter terms. Yet, independent of this finding, the claim that Eq. (14) itself (as it is presented in the Reply) stays invariant under transformation (8) is incorrect, which thus brings us to the next independent objection.[†]

Objection No. 5:

In the Reply on p. 4 after Eq. (19) it is said "As other terms in (14) remain invariant under (8), this finally proves the invariance ...". This statement is wrong, which already can be easily seen when transforming the convective term on the left-hand side of Eq. (14). It obviously does not stay invariant under transformation (8). Hence, this "proof" that the alleged symmetry for the unbounded LMN equations is also admitted by the bounded LMN equations is seriously flawed, in particular as we clearly proved opposite in Frewer *et al.* (2014).

Objection No. 6:

On p. 2 after Eq. (5) the statement "Here, the single [deterministic] velocity fields v and U are not rescaled [or changed] but the share of laminar solutions in the ensemble changes. This could be caused, e.g., by the change of initial conditions or external disturbances" is fictitious and unphysical. Because, how is it possible that if initial conditions change or external disturbances appear that then the underlying deterministic fields do not change?

[†]Important to note here is that Objection No. 4 discusses a different symmetry breaking mechanism than Objection No. 5. Both objections, and therefore also both symmetry breaking mechanisms, are of a different nature, which, as can be easily shown due to different parameter dependencies, cannot nullify each other. Hence we are ultimately confronted with a twofold breaking of the so-called "shape-symmetry".

Appendix: Green functions for rectangular duct and plane channel

The Green functions for a rectangular duct and a pure plane channel are given e.g. in Breit (1991) or Newman (1992). For the geometry of the plane channel the Green functions are identical in both Breit (1991) and Newman (1992), while for the rectangular duct they differ by a constant. Note that in order to do this comparison, one first has to transform the coordinates of the geometries accordingly, since Breit (1991) placed the geometries differently than Newman (1992). In the following we will take the approach and the formulas of Breit (1991).

The rectangular duct

In Breit (1991) the streamwise direction is given by the coordinate z and the wall-normal ones by x and y . The width $a > 0$ of the duct is defined in x direction ranging from $-a/2 \leq x \leq a/2$, while the height $b > 0$ is defined in the y direction ranging from $-b/2 \leq y \leq b/2$. Converting these definitions to the notation as used herein, we have to identify $z^{\text{Breit}} = x$ and $x^{\text{Breit}} = z$, i.e. we then have $a = 2L_z$ and $b = 2H$. Using this coordinate transformation, the Green function G for the rectangular duct when normalized inside its domain to $\nabla^2 G = -4\pi\delta^3(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}')$ and satisfying homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions is then given as (Breit, 1991, Eq. (3.2))[†]

$$\begin{aligned} G(x - x'; y, z, y', z'; a, b) &= G_0(x - x'; y - y', z - z'; 2a, 2b) \\ &+ G_0(x - x'; y + y' + b, z - z'; 2a, 2b) \\ &+ G_0(x - x'; y - y', z + z' + a; 2a, 2b) \\ &+ G_0(x - x'; y + y' + b, z + z' + a; 2a, 2b), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $G_0 = G_0(x; y, z; a, b)$ is the fundamental Green function of the considered geometry defined with the source point at the origin ($x' = 0, y' = 0, z' = 0$). It can be given in two different representations, either as (Breit, 1991, Eq. (2.2))

$$\begin{aligned} G_0(x; y, z; a, b) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}} \\ &+ \sum_{\substack{m, n = -\infty \\ |m| + |n| > 0}}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{x^2 + (y - nb)^2 + (z - ma)^2}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{(ma)^2 + (nb)^2}} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

or identically as (Breit, 1991, Eq. (10))

$$\begin{aligned} G_0(x; y, z; a, b) &= \frac{\lambda}{a} - \frac{2\pi}{ab}|x| \\ &+ \sum_{\substack{m, n = 0 \\ m+n > 0}}^{\infty} (4 - 2\delta_{m0} - 2\delta_{n0}) \frac{\exp\left(-2\pi|x|\sqrt{(m/a)^2 + (n/b)^2}\right)}{ab\sqrt{(m/a)^2 + (n/b)^2}} \cos(2\pi mz/a) \cos(2\pi ny/b), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where λ is the dimensionless constant

$$\lambda = 2\left(\ln(4\pi a/b) - \gamma\right) - 8 \sum_{m, n = 1}^{\infty} K_0(2\pi mnb/a), \quad (\text{A.4})$$

[†]Note that Breit (1991) typed in Eq. (3.2) the Green function for the positive domain $0 \leq x^{\text{Breit}_1} \leq a$ and $0 \leq y^{\text{Breit}_1} \leq b$, as correctly used in Newman (1992), and not for the actual domain $-a/2 \leq x^{\text{Breit}_2} \leq a/2$ and $-b/2 \leq y^{\text{Breit}_2} \leq b/2$. For the latter domain the Green function has to be transformed accordingly, namely by $x^{\text{Breit}_2} = x^{\text{Breit}_1} - a/2$ and $y^{\text{Breit}_2} = y^{\text{Breit}_1} - b/2$. In (A.1) the variables are then renamed as $x^{\text{Breit}_2} = z$, $y^{\text{Breit}_2} = y$ and $z^{\text{Breit}_2} = x$.

with γ as Euler's constant and K_0 as the zeroth order modified Bessel function of the second kind. The latter representation (A.3) has the great advantage that it not only explicitly shows its counter-intuitive property of being periodic in each of the two wall-normal directions, but also that it explicitly reveals its far-field scaling behavior for $|x| \rightarrow \infty$. Important to note here is that since this Green function does not satisfy homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions in the streamwise direction, it does not serve as a universal Green function of the general Neumann problem. A universal Green function for the duct can be found for example in Polyanin (2002), which instead of $|x|$ then asymptotically scales as $e^{-|x|}$. Finally note that formula (A.3) was given in Breit (1991) only for $a = 1$.

The plane channel

In contrast to the duct, the plane channel is fully unbounded in two directions. In Breit (1991) the streamwise, spanwise and wall-normal direction is given by the coordinates z , y and x respectively. The width or height $a > 0$ of the channel is thus defined in the x direction ranging from $-a/2 \leq x \leq a/2$. Converting these definitions again to the notation as used herein, we have to identify $z^{\text{Breit}} = x$, $y^{\text{Breit}} = z$ and $x^{\text{Breit}} = y$, for which we then have $a = 2H$. Using this coordinate transformation and renaming the parameter $a = 2H$ to $b = 2H$, the Green function G for the plane channel when normalized again inside its domain to $\nabla^2 G = -4\pi\delta^3(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}')$ and satisfying homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions is then given as (Breit, 1991, Eq. (3.1))[†]

$$G(x - x', z - z'; y, y'; b) = G_0(x - x', z - z'; y - y'; 2b) + G_0(x - x', z - z'; y + y' + b; 2b), \quad (\text{A.5})$$

where $G_0 = G_0(x, z; y; b)$ is now the fundamental Green function of the considered geometry of a plane channel defined with the source point at the origin ($x' = 0, x' = 0, z' = 0$). As before for the duct, it can also be given in two different representations, either as (Breit, 1991, Eq. (2.1))

$$G_0(x, z; y; b) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}} + \sum_{\substack{n=-\infty \\ n \neq 0}}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{x^2 + (y - nb)^2 + z^2}} - \frac{1}{|nb|} \right), \quad (\text{A.6})$$

or identically as (Breit, 1991, Eq. (4))[‡]

$$G_0(x, z; y; b) = -\frac{2}{b} \left(\gamma + \ln \frac{\sqrt{x^2 + z^2}}{2b} \right) + \frac{4}{b} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} K_0(2\pi n \sqrt{x^2 + z^2}/b) \cos(2\pi ny/b), \quad (\text{A.7})$$

with γ again as Euler's constant and K_0 as the zeroth order modified Bessel function of the second kind. Note the crucial difference between the single-periodic function (A.7) for plane channel and the double-periodic function (A.3) for the rectangular duct, which expresses itself in the fact that in the far-field the latter one scales as $|x|$ while the former one only as $\ln|x|$ for $x \rightarrow \infty$ and a finite-valued coordinate z , since the modified Bessel function K_0 decays exponentially for large values of its argument. Finally, it's worthwhile to note that although the plane channel can be geometrically seen as the limiting case of the duct for $a = 2L_z \rightarrow \infty$, this is not the case for the Green functions. The function (A.7) does *not* follow from (A.3) in the limit $a \rightarrow \infty$, but rather, by definition, only from its complementary limit $a \rightarrow 0$, which can be readily seen when comparing the identical representations (A.6) and (A.2) respectively.

[†]Note that Breit (1991) typed in Eq. (3.1) the Green function for the domain $0 \leq x^{\text{Breit}_1} \leq a$, as correctly used in Newman (1992), and not for the actual domain $-a/2 \leq x^{\text{Breit}_2} \leq a/2$. For the latter domain the Green function has to be transformed accordingly, namely by $x^{\text{Breit}_2} = x^{\text{Breit}_1} - a/2$. In (A.5) the variables are then renamed as $x^{\text{Breit}_2} = y$, $y^{\text{Breit}_2} = z$ and $z^{\text{Breit}_2} = x$, as well as the parameter $a^{\text{Breit}} = b$.

[‡]Breit (1991) missed a factor four in front of the sum. Also note that formula (A.7) was given in Breit (1991) only for $b = 1$ again.

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